

Supplemental material to Olijhoek et al. Feeding up to 91% concentrate to Holstein and Jersey dairy cows: Effects on enteric methane emission, rumen fermentation and bacterial community, digestibility, production, and feeding behavior

Figure S1.

Heatmap of the Spearman rank correlation between the relative abundance of rumen bacterial species and molar proportions of VFA in rumen liquid (mol/100 mol), hydrogen production (g/d), and methane emission (g/d and g/kg of DMI) across breed and diet. Significant correlations are indicated with a plus (+) symbol. The species or species level groups are labeled with the name for the order, genus, and species (if applicable).

